

CHILD-PARENT RELATIONSHIPS IN SINGLE-PARENT FAMILIES.**Rustamova Mo‘tabar Ravshanovna**

Lecturer of the Department of pedagogy and Psychology,

University of Alfraganus

Email: rustamova.motabar@bk.ru[ORCID: 0009-0006-8118-2185](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8118-2185)

Abstract: The topic of psychological peculiarities of children's attitudes to parents in complete and incomplete families, considered in this thesis, by its relevance deserves attention not only of specialists in the fields of psychology and pedagogy, but also, first of all, of parents and educators of children's school institutions. The considered topic has recently become relevant and has aroused increased interest of both domestic specialists, which was the reason for the emergence of a large number of scientific articles and literature on this issue. In Russia at the present time there are serious changes in the conditions of personality formation, there are difficult conditions of economic and political instability, there is a breakdown of traditional values and therefore the problem of psychological features in complete and incomplete families in adolescence is relevant. The analysis of theoretical material allowed us to draw the following conclusions: any deformation of the family leads to negative consequences in the development of the child's personality.

Key words: complete family, incomplete family, child, family relations, upbringing, environment, parents.

Introduction. An incomplete family is a group of immediate relatives consisting of one parent with one or more minor children. An incomplete family arises for various reasons: birth of a child out of wedlock, death of one of the parents, dissolution of marriage or separation of parents. Accordingly, the main types of incomplete family are distinguished - non-marital, orphaned, divorced, broken up. There is also a

distinction between paternal and maternal families, which constitute the absolute majority of single-parent families. As B.C.Mukhina notes, the upbringing of children in an incomplete family has a number of peculiarities. Due to the absence of one of the parents, the remaining parent has to take on himself the solution of all material and domestic problems of the family. At the same time, he also needs to fill the resulting deficit of educational influence on children. It is very difficult to combine all these tasks. Therefore, most single-parent families experience material and domestic difficulties and face pedagogical problems. The psychological climate of a single-parent family is largely determined by the painful experiences resulting from the absence of one of the parents[1].

According to J.Langmeyer and Z.Matejcek, in a family each individual member fulfills naturally, spontaneously a certain role and satisfies the child's vital needs - physical, emotional, intellectual and moral. If a family lacks a key member, there is easily a danger of deprivation for the child, because it is not always possible to substitute the role that this family member would have to fulfill in relation to the child and in relation to the whole family unit. According to the studies of E.O.Smirnova and B.C.Sobkin, the most common styles of upbringing in incomplete families are unstable style of upbringing, hypoprotection, condoning hyperprotection, emotional rejection. Under the unstable style of upbringing is understood inconsistency, unmotivated emotional manifestations, when praise or rebuke depends on the mood, not on the objective behavior of the child. As a result of such upbringing, the child learns the fact that everything that happens depends not on his behavior, but on external causes.[5]

Ultimately, he/she refuses to try to understand the cause-and-effect relations of the surrounding society, does not analyze the conformity of his/her actions to social norms, is unable to evaluate his/her experiences and actions. Hypoprotection type of upbringing means low attention to the child. In this case, parents are very little interested in the affairs, successes, experiences of the child. Formally, prohibitions and rules in the family exist, requirements to the child are made, but parents do not control

their fulfillment. The situation of uncontrollability and even neglect of the child is caused either by parents' indifference or by their excessive busyness, concentration on other life problems. If hypoprotection is combined with good emotional contact, such a child grows up in a situation of permissiveness, he does not develop the habit of organization, planning his behavior. Such children have difficulty with self-regulation. To serious negative consequences leads to education in conditions of hypoprotection in combination with emotional coldness of parents. In this case, the child constantly feels his needlessness, lack of affection and love, and these experiences contribute to the formation of an inferiority complex, high aggressiveness. This type of upbringing is most often found in socially disadvantaged families.

Where parents abuse alcohol, lead an immoral lifestyle, children are usually neglected, left to their own devices, deprived of basic care and concern; physical punishment is often used against children. Increased attention to the child in combination with close emotional contact, full acceptance of all behavioral manifestations means education by the type of condoning hyperprotection.

In this case, parents strive to fulfill any whim of the child, to protect him from difficulties, troubles, grief. In such a family, the child is always in the center of attention, he is an object of adoration, the "idol of the family". "Blind" love encourages parents to exaggerate his abilities, not to notice the negative qualities, to create an atmosphere of admiration and praise around the child. As a result, children form egocentrism, inflated self-esteem, intolerance of difficulties and obstacles on the way to the satisfaction of desires. They see themselves as standing beyond criticism, condemnation and remarks. They explain their failures by the injustice of others or accidental circumstances. Therefore, the personality formed in the conditions of upbringing by the type of condoning hyperprotection, very often experiences negative feelings at the first encounters with reality.

According to a number of researchers (A.I. Zakharov, A.I. Furmanov, A.S. Semenyuk), parental ill-will or inattention causes unconscious mutual hostility in

children. This hostility can be manifested both explicitly, in relation to the parents themselves, and implicitly. Unaccountable, unmotivated cruelty shown by some children is often a consequence of childhood experiences. If this aggression is directed inward, it becomes the cause of low self-esteem, guilt and anxiety.[6]

The child is coddled, his or her needs are ignored, and sometimes abused. Parents (or their "substitutes" - stepmother, stepfather, etc.) consider the child a burden and show general dissatisfaction with the child. Hidden emotional rejection is common: parents try to disguise their real attitude to the child with increased care and attention to the child. This style has the most negative impact on the child's development. Cruel relationships can be manifested openly, when the child takes out his anger, using violence, or be hidden, when between the parents and the child is a "wall" of emotional coldness and hostility. Another type of parenting is increased moral responsibility.

Conclusion. They demand honesty, integrity and a sense of duty from a child inappropriately for his or her age. Ignoring the interests and capabilities of the child, they make him/her responsible for the well-being of relatives. The role of "head of the family" is forcibly attributed to him. Parents hope for a special future for their child, and the child is afraid to disappoint them. Often he is entrusted with the care of younger children or the elderly. Increased moral responsibility causes aggression, as well as anxiety and fears. Psychological studies (A.I. Zakharov, A.S. Spivakovskaya, E.O. Smirnova, B.C. Sobkin, J. Langmeyer, Z. Mateychek, etc.) show that due to the above-mentioned reasons children from incomplete families, as compared to their peers from complete families, have a number of psychological features, which in most cases have a pronounced negative character[2,3,4]. Thus, A.S.Spivakovskaya states that children from incomplete families, in comparison with their peers from complete families, have lower school performance, are more prone to neurotic disorders and illegal behavior. As a result of studies of school-age children brought up in incomplete families, infantilization, low self-esteem, negative attitudes towards parents, and gender role behavior disorders were revealed in them.

Literature

1. Andreeva A.D., Vokhmyanina T.V., Voronova A.P., Chutkina N.I. / edited by Dubrovina M.V./. Manual of practical psychologist. Mental health of children and adolescents. Moscow, 1995.
2. Buyanov M.I. A child from a dysfunctional family. M., 1988.
3. Kolesnichenko E.A. "Psychological problems of the modern Russian family" In 3 parts. - 2 parts / Under the general editorship of Doctor of Psychological Sciences V.K. Shabelnikov and Candidate of Psychological Sciences A.G. Lidars. - M., 2005. - 360 c.
4. Kolesov D.V. Talks about Sex Education. - Moscow: Pedagogy, 1980. - 192c. - (Book for parents).
5. Matejcek Z. Some psychological problems of upbringing of children in an incomplete family// Upbringing of children in an incomplete family/ translation from Czech Khvatalova L.N., ed. and afterword by N.M. Ershova - M.: Progress, 1980. - c. 70-98
6. Rubinstein S.Ya. Character traits of the child and their upbringing in the family. A book for parents. - Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1964. - 48 c.
7. Raimdjanov, M. T., Raimdjanova, G. B. (2023). Talabalarning ijodiy faoliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi psixologik omillarning nazariy tahlili. Markaziy osiyoda jamiyat, gender va oila, 3(8), 126-129.
8. Raimdjanov, M. T., Tohirova, H. L. (2023). Yoshlarning turli xil yot g'oyalarga berilishlarining ayrim ijtimoiy psixologik masalalari. Markaziy osiyoda jamiyat, gender va oila, 2(7), 81-84.
9. Raimdjanov, M. T. (2023). Internet tarmog'ida shaxs kommunikativ xulq-atvorinipsixologik xususiyatlari. Yosh avlodning psixologik salomatligi – davlat siyosatining ustuvor vazifasi, 1(1), 307-311.

10. Raimdjanov, M. (2021). Cooperation between school, family and community on vocational training of students as a social pedagogical problem. Conferencious Online, 28-30.
11. Norqo'ziyev, D., & Raimdjanov, M. (2021, October). Characteristics of Formation of a Sense of Professional Responsibility in Psychological Students. " Online-conferences" platform (pp. 178-181).
12. Norqo'ziyev, D., Raimdjanov, D. (2021). Sharq allomalari asarlarida o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish muammosining psixologik talqini. Инновационное образование международный опыт, 1(1), 462-463.
13. Raimdjanov, M. T. (2021). Maktabgacha yosh davri bolalarda o'zini-o'zi anglashning psixologik jihatlari. Pedagogika, 1(4), 110-112.
14. Raimdjanov, M. (2021). Formation of pedagogical and psychological knowledge in future teachers. Scientific progress, 2(4), 988-991.
15. Алимova, Г. К., & Раимджанов, М. Т. Здоровьесберегающие педагогические технологии как фактор обеспечения здорового образа жизни (на примере ДОУ).
16. G Ibragimova, M Raimdjanov [PEDAGOGLARNI TALABALAR BILAN HAMKORLIK O'RNATISH SOHASIDAGI TAJRIBALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH](#) To'plam, 2019.
17. N.Khasanova, Z.Dekhkonboyeva // Motivational determinants of youth involvement in fitness practices. "Узбекистан 2030: наука, образование и экономика в развитии"15.10.2023 Tashkent. Uzbekistan p81-85.
18. Н.Хасанова Психологические исследования приверженности личности лечению//ВЕСТНИК ИНТЕГРАТИВНОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ // Журнал для психологов. Вып. 28. 2023. С.454-458
19. З.Д. Дехконбоева Психологические факторы вовлеченности в фитнес практики. Бухара - Ярославль: МАПН, 2023. «Вестник интегративной психологии. Журнал для психологов. Вып. 30. Часть2» 115-121.

20. З.Д. Дехконбоева Самоэффективность как предикт изучения вовлеченности личности в фитнес практики. Мирзо Улугбек номидаги ЎзМУ, 2023. «Личность и общество: вызовы современности». с. 304-307